

SWIPT with Diplexer-based Multiple-Antenna Rectification

Eleni Goudeli, Constantinos Psomas, and Ioannis Krikidis
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus
Email: {egoude01, psomas, krikidis}@ucy.ac.cy

Abstract—Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT), with the use of radio frequency (RF) signals, has been identified as one of the promising technologies for the Internet of Things (IoT). In order to practically achieve SWIPT the received RF signal is split in time, power or spatial domain. Even for the solution of the integrated SWIPT receiver, the converted direct current power signal is split in the power domain. As such a portion of the received signal is used for information decoding and the other for energy harvesting (EH). Recently, a scheme which achieves SWIPT without split of the resources, with the use of a diplexer at the receiver's side, was proposed. In this paper, we adopt this solution and we extend it to a diplexer-based SWIPT receiver, with multiple-antenna rectification circuits. As such we succeed SWIPT with enhanced performance, both in terms of symbol error rate and EH. We further compare the solution to the conventional integrated SWIPT receiver with multiple rectennas and prove the enhanced performance of the proposed solution. Non-coherent energy detection is succeeded with the use of a maximum-likelihood soft decoder, while the adopted modulation scheme is on-off keying (OOK). Furthermore, we investigate the effect of pulse energy modulation (PEM) in the system's performance. It is shown that PEM scheme enhances the performance in terms of EH, while lags behind in terms of information decoding, compared to OOK.

Keywords—SWIPT, diplexers, integrated receiver, energy detection, ML-based soft decoding.

I. INTRODUCTION

Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) has been recognized as one of the promising technologies for handling the explosive growth of Internet of Things (IoT) in 5G networks [1]. This is due to the fact, that battery-powered wireless communication devices have limited energy storage capacity and their frequent replacement can be costly or even impossible. Also, we should consider the cases where wireless sensor modules will be unobtrusively and invisibly integrated into clothing, walls, and vehicles at locations which are inaccessible for wired/manual recharging.

A promising approach to prolong the lifetime of traditional wireless communication systems is to enable the wireless communication of the devices by harvesting energy from the environment [2]. Unfortunately, these conventional natural

energy sources are usually climate and location dependent, which may be a barrier for IoT solutions. As such, radio-frequency (RF) signals, are considered as a viable source for SWIPT, since they have the ability to energize devices over a long distance, while have been widely used for wireless information transmission.

Despite the continuous advances in SWIPT technology, there are some key challenges for practical implementations. In the literature of RF circuits, it is impossible to perform SWIPT from the same received signal by using one antenna [3]. As such, SWIPT is achieved through a separated receiver in time, power or spatial domain, where the received RF signal is split for information decoding (ID) and energy harvesting (EH) [4]. Furthermore, authors in [5], propose and study an integrated SWIPT receiver, where the RF to baseband conversion is replaced from a passive rectifier operation, which results in a direct current (DC) power signal. Afterwards, the DC signal is also split in the power domain, for ID and EH.

The work in [6], proposes a new scheme which achieves SWIPT without split of the resources. Authors show that the same RF received signal can be used for both ID and EH, with the use of an RF diplexer at the receiver's side. Diplexers are passive devices that implement frequency-domain multiplexing. In particular, their ports are frequency-selective, while reversing their input and output, can be used for separating higher from lower frequency signals, at one receive antenna. As such, with the proposed circuit, there is no need for a power splitter, since the low-pass band-pass diplexer allows the dual and continuous use of the same signal for SWIPT.

One of the main issues in SWIPT is the efficient ID, along with the energy that is being harvested. In the state-of-the-art, multiple antenna system models are traditionally considered as a common solution for enhanced performance either in terms of ID or EH. Specifically, in [7], authors investigate SWIPT with a multi-antenna transmitter sending data and energy to single antenna receivers adopting a time switching circuit. Beamforming for energy transfer and information transmission is considered in [8], achieving the optimal energy efficiency. Finally, regarding the ID, coherent techniques are a challenging task, since the source needs to periodically send training symbols, which results in increased signaling overhead and processing burden [9]. On the contrary, the receivers complexity is reduced with non-coherent techniques..

Motivated by the above, in this paper we propose a topology

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Fig. 1. Architecture of the diplexer-based SWIPT receiver.

with the use of an RF circuit implementation with multiple diplexers. As such we achieve SWIPT with enhanced performance, both in terms of ID and EH. We further succeed non-coherent decoding, with the use of a maximum likelihood (ML)-based soft decoder. In particular, we examine the performance of the proposed solution, by adopting two different modulation schemes, i.e. binary on-off keying (OOK) and pulse energy modulation (PEM), appropriate for energy detection. We further compare the performance of the proposed system model to the conventional integrated receiver, with multiple rectennas. Simulation results fully validate the theoretical analysis and confirm the benefits of the proposed diplexer-based receiver. Finally, we show that PEM enhances the EH, though deteriorates the ID, compared to OOK.

Notation: Lowercase boldface letters denote vectors; $\mathbb{P}(X)$ denotes the probability of the event X , $\mathbb{E}[X]$ represents the expected value of X ; $f(y)$ denotes the probability density function (pdf) of y and $\Re\{\cdot\}$ the real part of a complex number. Finally, $\gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $\Gamma(\cdot, \cdot)$ denote the lower and upper incomplete gamma function, respectively, while $\Gamma(\cdot)$ the ordinary gamma function.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

As seen in Fig. 1, we consider a single input multiple output SWIPT system. The source transmits from a single antenna, a baseband signal $x(t)$ with $\mathbb{E}[x^2(t)] = 1$. At the receiver's side we consider K antennas, each one connected to a diode, followed by a diplexer. The modulation scheme adopted is OOK, while symbols $x \in [0, 1]$, are transmitted with equal probability.

Then, the up-converted RF signal is transmitted over a Rayleigh fading channel, with average transmit power P and we assume that f is the carrier frequency. The signal propagates through a wireless channel gain $h_j > 0$, where $j \in [1, \dots, K]$ and phase shift $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$. As such, the transmitted RF band signal is given by $\sqrt{2P}\Re\{x(t)e^{j2\pi ft}\}$. The noise from a receiving antenna j , is modeled as an additive Gaussian noise (AWGN) i.e. $\sqrt{2}\Re\{n_j(t)e^{j2\pi ft}\}$.

Therefore, the received RF signal at an antenna j is

$$y_j(t) = \sqrt{2}\Re\{h_j\sqrt{P}x(t)e^{j(2\pi ft + \theta)} + n_j(t)e^{j2\pi ft}\} \quad (1)$$

$$= \sqrt{2}\mu_{y_j}(t) \cos(2\pi ft + \phi_{y_j}(t)), \quad (2)$$

where

$$\phi_{y_j}(t) = \arctan \frac{\mu_{I_j}(t)}{\mu_{R_j}(t)}, \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_{y_j}(t) = \sqrt{\mu_{R_j}(t)^2 + \mu_{I_j}(t)^2}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mu_{R_j}(t) = h_j\sqrt{P}x(t) \cos(\phi(t) + \theta) + n_{R_j}(t), \quad (5)$$

$$\mu_{I_j}(t) = h_j\sqrt{P}x(t) \sin(\phi(t) + \theta) + n_{I_j}(t), \quad (6)$$

where n_{R_j} and n_{I_j} denote the real and imaginary part of complex AWGN at each receive antenna j , respectively.

At each antenna j , the received RF signal $y_j(t)$ is converted to DC signal $i_j(t)$, with the use of a single Schottky diode. With an input voltage proportional to $y_j(t)$, the current harmonics through the first diode can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} i_j(t) &= I_s(e^{\gamma y_j(t)} - 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{I_s}{n!} (\gamma y_j(t))^n \\ &= \alpha_1 y_j(t) + \alpha_2 y_j^2(t) + \alpha_3 y_j^3(t) + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where I_s is the saturation current, γ denotes the reciprocal of the thermal voltage of the Schottky diode, and the coefficients α_n 's are given by $\alpha_n = I_s \gamma^n / n!$, with $n = 1, 2, \dots$, due to the expansion of the exponential function. By ignoring the higher-order (larger than two) terms of $y_j(t)$, we obtain the output current from the first diode, as follows

$$\begin{aligned} i_j(t) &\approx \sqrt{2}\alpha_1 \mu_{y_j}(t) \cos(2\pi ft + \phi_{y_j}(t)) \\ &\quad + 2\alpha_2 \mu_{y_j}^2(t) \cos^2(2\pi ft + \phi_{y_j}(t)) \\ &= \alpha_2 \mu_{y_j}^2(t) + \sqrt{2}\alpha_1 \mu_{y_j}(t) \cos(2\pi ft + \phi_{y_j}(t)) \\ &\quad + \alpha_2 \mu_{y_j}^2(t) \cos(4\pi ft + 2\phi_{y_j}(t)). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The output current $i_j(t)$ at each receive antenna j , is then channeled as input to a diplexer, which is processed by a low-pass filter (LPF) and a pass-band filter. As such, the diplexer successfully separates the low frequency components from the higher ones, as those described in (8).

Specifically, the LPF in the diplexer, removes the high-frequency harmonics at both f and $2f$ and a DC signal

$$i_{DC_{1j}}(t) = \alpha_2 \mu_{y_j}^2(t), \quad (9)$$

appears as one of the outputs of the diplexer. The DC outputs from all the K diplexers are added with the use of a DC combiner and then channeled to charge the battery and store the energy. Since α_2 is a constant specified by the diode, for convenience we assume in the sequel that $\alpha_2 \approx 1$. Furthermore, substituting (5) and (6) into (4) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{y_j}^2 &= (h_j\sqrt{P}x(t) \cos(\phi(t) + \theta) + n_{R_j}(t))^2 \\ &\quad + (h_j\sqrt{P}x(t) \sin(\phi(t) + \theta) + n_{I_j}(t))^2. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

For convenience we re-express (10) as follows

$$\mu_{y_j}^2(t) = |h_j \sqrt{P} x e^{j(\phi(t)+\theta)} + n_j(t)|^2. \quad (11)$$

Since planar rotation does not change the statistics of $n_j(t)$, (11) can be equivalently written as

$$\mu_{y_j}^2 = |h_j \sqrt{P} x + n_j|^2. \quad (12)$$

Following our analysis, the suppressed signals from the LPF of the diplexer are used as the second output of the diplexer from the pass-band filter. Without loss of generality, we keep only the main harmonic at f and remove the higher harmonics at $2f$, i.e. $\sqrt{2}\alpha_1\mu_{y_j}(t) \cos(2\pi ft + \phi_{y_j}(t))$. This signal is also used as input to the second diode.

Subsequently, the output current of the second diode is now processed by a LPF, through which all high-frequency harmonic components are removed. As such the DC signal from a received antenna j , that appears as the output of the second diode and input of the analog-to-digital converter (ADC), is

$$i_{\text{DC}_{2j}} = \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2 \mu_{y_j}^2, \quad (13)$$

where we assume that $\alpha_1^2 \alpha_2 \approx 1$. Herein, we note that both the harmonics of f and $2f$ have been removed, while as in the first diode the noise from the rectifier is considered negligible.

Considering that channel state information (CSI) is available at the receiver, coherent detection is adopted, while soft decoding is succeeded with the use of ML. As seen in Fig. 1, the decoder of the proposed diplexer-based SWIPT receiver, samples and decodes, the DC outputs, i.e. $i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}$, from K diodes. The optimum decision rule, is based on the observation vector $\mathbf{i}_{\text{DC}_2} = [i_{\text{DC}_{21}}, \dots, i_{\text{DC}_{2K}}]$. The symbol that yields the maximum conditioned density $f(\mathbf{i}_{\text{DC}_2}|x)$ is selected

$$\tilde{x} = \arg \max_{x \in (0,1)} f(\mathbf{i}_{\text{DC}_2}|x). \quad (14)$$

Assuming that the noise is independent between different receive antennas, the distribution can be factored as

$$f(\mathbf{i}_{\text{DC}_2}|x) = \prod_{j=1}^{j=K} f(i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}|x), \quad (15)$$

where $f(i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}|x)$ denotes the conditional probability density function (pdf) of $i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}$, considering that x is transmitted. From (12) and (13), we notice that $i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}$ is exponentially distributed with pdf

$$f(i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}) = \lambda_x e^{-\lambda_x i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}}, \quad (16)$$

where λ_x denotes the rate parameter and is calculated from

$$\lambda_x = 1/\mathbb{E}(i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}) = 1/(Px^2 + 1), \quad (17)$$

as such we herein define $\lambda_0 = 1$ and $\lambda_1 = 1/(P + 1)$.

Therefore, the final decision on the transmitted symbol is based on the following criterion

$$\prod_{j=1}^{j=K} f(i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}|0) \underset{\tilde{x}=1}{\overset{\tilde{x}=0}{\geq}} \prod_{j=1}^{j=K} f(i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}|1). \quad (18)$$

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this section, we study the performance of the proposed diplexer-based SWIPT receiver, for the ID and EH.

A. Symbol Error Rate

As seen in Fig. 1 the received RF power at each receive antenna $j \in [1, K]$, results in a DC power signal, $i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}$ which is used for ID. The decoder decides on the transmitted symbol \tilde{x} , with the use of ML and (18). As such, we herein calculate the total probability of error, from the following Lemma.

Lemma 1. *The total probability of error for the SWIPT receiver with multiple diplexers is*

$$P_D = \frac{1}{2\Gamma(K)} \left(\gamma(K, \lambda_1 t) + \Gamma(K, t) \right), \quad (19)$$

where

$$t = \frac{K}{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_0)} \ln \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_0} \right). \quad (20)$$

Proof. See Appendix A. \square

B. Average Energy Harvested

For the computation of the average energy that is being harvested we consider a conversion efficiency of $\zeta = 0.7$ [11]. As seen in Fig. 1, the output from the LPF of each diplexer, provides at each receive antenna j , a DC output, i.e. $i_{\text{DC}_{1j}}$, given from (9) and (12). All these outputs from the K antennas are summed with the use of a DC combiner and channeled to the battery for EH. As such the average EH is given by

$$\begin{aligned} Q_D &= \zeta \sum_{j=1}^{j=K} \sum_{x \in (0,1)} \mathbb{P}(x) \mathbb{E}[i_{\text{DC}_{1j}}] \\ &= \frac{\zeta}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{j=K} \sum_{x \in (0,1)} \int_0^\infty i_{\text{DC}_{1j}} f(i_{\text{DC}_{1j}}) di_{\text{DC}_{1j}} = \frac{1}{2} K \zeta \alpha_2 P. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

We herein note that $i_{\text{DC}_{1j}}$ follows the exponential distribution as $i_{\text{DC}_{2j}}$ and the pdf is given from (16). This is due to the assumption that $\alpha_1^2 \alpha_2 \approx 1$. As such from (9) and (13) $i_{\text{DC}_{1j}} = i_{\text{DC}_{2j}} = \mu_{y_j}^2$. Furthermore, we assume that the noise introduced by each rectifier, i.e. n_j , is a small constant and thus ignored for the EH.

Conventional Integrated SWIPT Receiver [5]: Herein, we compare the proposed system model with the solution of an integrated SWIPT receiver with multiple rectennas, in terms of SER and EH [11]. The received power signal at each receive antenna of the integrated receiver, activates the rectifier and provides a DC power signal as output of the LPF. This signal is the same as the DC output, $i_{\text{DC}_{1j}}$, in our proposed system model. Thereafter, a splitter is used and a portion ρ of the DC power signal is used for ID and $1 - \rho$ for EH, with $\rho \in (0, 1)$. Similarly, the decoder decides on the transmitted symbol \tilde{x} , with the use of ML and soft decoding.

The total probability of error, is derived by using the following Proposition.

Fig. 2. SER of the proposed diplexer-based SWIPT receiver compared to conventional integrated SWIPT receiver; for $K = 2, 4$ and $\rho = 0.4$.

Proposition 1. *The probability of error, in terms of SER, for the conventional integrated SWIPT receiver, with multiple rectennas at the receiver's side, is given by*

$$P_I = \frac{1}{2\Gamma(K)} \left(\gamma(K, \lambda_1 \rho t) + \Gamma(K, \rho t) \right). \quad (22)$$

Proof. See Appendix B. \square

The average EH is derived considering that $(1-\rho)$ of the DC output from each receive antenna j , is used for EH. As such, following the same steps as in the proposed system model of the diplexer-based SWIPT receiver, the average EH is

$$Q_I = (1 - \rho)Q_D = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \rho)K\zeta\alpha_2 P. \quad (23)$$

C. Pulse Energy Modulation

For the sake of comparison, we additionally study a different modulation scheme. It has to be noticed, that the analysis is general for energy detection, while what changes with the different adopted modulation schemes, is the rate parameters. More specifically, the modulation scheme used by the transmitter for comparison, is PEM, with M energy levels. We design our energy pulse based symbol alphabet, based on equi-spaced amplitudes as in [10]. Specifically, we assume that a set of M symbols $x_i \in \{1d, 2d, \dots, Md\}$, are mapped to each energy level, where d is the distance between the energy pulse based symbols. Therefore, we have

$$\mathbb{E}[x^2(t)] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M x_i^2 = \frac{d^2}{6}(M+1)(2M+1) = 1, \quad (24)$$

which results in

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{6}{(M+1)(2M+1)}}. \quad (25)$$

Herein, we need to consider that with PEM, the rate parameters given from (17) are now defined as $\lambda_{x_i} = 1/(Px_i^2 + 1) = 1/(P(id)^2 + 1)$, with $i \in [1, M]$.

Fig. 3. EH of the proposed diplexer-based SWIPT receiver compared to conventional integrated SWIPT receiver; $K = 2, 4$ and $\rho = 0.4$.

Fig. 4. SER and Q_D , of the proposed diplexer-based SWIPT receiver for OOK and PEM; $M = 2$ and $K = 4$.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we provide numerical results and illustrate the performance of our proposed system model. Monte-Carlo simulations are carried out and all the outcomes presented are calculated for 10^6 iterations.

In Fig. 2 we present the performance of the proposed diplexer-based SWIPT receiver, in terms of SER, for $K = 2$ and $K = 4$. Furthermore, we compare it with the performance of the conventional integrated receiver with multiple rectennas. With the increase of the average transmitted power P , the performance for both schemes is enhanced, while the diplexer-based SWIPT receiver is superior, for the same number of receive antennas K . Something that was expected, since in the solution of the integrated receiver, only a portion ρ of the DC power signal is used for ID.

In Fig. 3 we illustrate the performance of the proposed

SWIPT receiver in terms of EH. We show that the diplexer-based SWIPT receiver enhances the average EH, compared to the integrated SWIPT receiver. This is because a portion $(1 - \rho)$ of the DC signal is used for EH, while in the scheme of the diplexer-based solution, the DC output from the first diode is used in the whole.

For the sake of comparison, in Fig. 4, we illustrate the performance of the diplexer-based SWIPT receiver, by adopting OOK and PEM, for $M = 2$ and $K = 4$. PEM enhances the average EH, while deteriorates the ID, resulting in error floor.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we study a non-coherent detection scheme for a diplexer-based SWIPT receiver. More specifically, we consider a topology with K receive antennas, each one connected to a diplexer. With the adopted system model, we succeed ID and EH without split of the resources in time, power or spatial domain. Furthermore, with the use of a multiple-antenna receiver, we enhance the performance, both in terms of ID and EH. In addition, we compare the proposed solution to the conventional integrated SWIPT receiver with multiple rectennas, proving the enhanced performance. Finally, energy detection is succeeded, with the use of a ML-based soft decoder, while we compare OOK modulation scheme to PEM. We show that PEM scheme results in enhanced EH, while deteriorates the ID. For future work, we will investigate how harvested energy varies for different path loss model and study a multiple input multiple output system model.

APPENDIX A

By substituting (16) and (17) into (18), we have

$$i_{\text{DC}21} + i_{\text{DC}22} + \dots + i_{\text{DC}2K} \stackrel{\bar{x}=1}{\underset{\bar{x}=0}{\gtrless}} \frac{K}{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_0)} \ln \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_0} \right), \quad (26)$$

where we set the right part of inequality equal to t and the left part $u = \sum_{j=1}^{j=K} i_{\text{DC}2j}$. Taking into consideration that $i_{\text{DC}2j}$ follows the exponential distribution from (16), then by considering [12, Ch.1.8.7], we conclude that u follows the Erlang distribution, which results in

$$f(u) = \frac{u^{K-1} e^{-\lambda_x u} \lambda_x^K}{\Gamma(K)}. \quad (27)$$

Following our analysis, the total probability of error is

$$P_D = \mathbb{P}(u < t|x = 1) + \mathbb{P}(u > t|x = 0) \\ = \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_0^t f(u|x = 1) du + \int_t^\infty f(u|x = 0) du \right). \quad (28)$$

By substituting (27) and the appropriate calculations with the use of (17), (19) is derived.

APPENDIX B

For the integrated receiver, a portion $\rho \in (0, 1)$ of the DC power signal is channeled to the decoder for ID. Following the same analysis as for the proposed diplexer-based SWIPT system model, it is shown that this power signal is the same

as the DC output of the diplexer, i.e. $i_{\text{DC}1j}$. As such, it is exponentially distributed, with rate parameter equal to

$$\lambda'_x = 1/\mathbb{E}(\rho i_{\text{DC}1j}) = \frac{1}{\rho(Px^2 + 1)} = \frac{\lambda_x}{\rho}, \quad (29)$$

and the pdf is expressed as

$$f(\rho i_{\text{DC}1j}) = \frac{\lambda_x}{\rho} e^{-\frac{\lambda_x}{\rho} i_{\text{DC}1j}}. \quad (30)$$

Substituting (30) in (18), and the appropriate calculations with the use of (29), the ML criterion follows

$$i_{\text{DC}11} + i_{\text{DC}12} + \dots + i_{\text{DC}1K} \stackrel{\bar{x}=1}{\underset{\bar{x}=0}{\gtrless}} \frac{\rho K}{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_0)} \ln \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_0} \right), \quad (31)$$

where the right part of (31) is equal to $t' = \rho t$. We note also that the left part is equal to $u = \sum_{j=1}^{j=K} i_{\text{DC}1j}$ as defined in Appendix A, with pdf given from (27).

Therefore the total probability of error is given by

$$P_I = \mathbb{P}(u < t'|x = 1) + \mathbb{P}(u > t'|x = 0) \\ = \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_0^{t'} f(u|x = 1) du + \int_{t'}^\infty f(u|x = 0) du \right), \quad (32)$$

where by substituting $t' = \rho t$, (22) is derived.

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